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Real Time Health Monitoring System

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and implementation of a low-power wearable health monitoring system based on the Nordic nRF52840. The system integrates a 6-axis Inertial Measurement Unit (3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope) for step detection and motion tracking, along with the MAX30100 optical sensor for heart rate and SpO₂ monitoring. The collected physiological and motion data are processed using embedded algorithms to estimate calorie intake and calorie expenditure in real time. The device uses Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) for wireless transmission to a mobile system for visualization and long-term analytics. Experimental results demonstrate improved accuracy in step counting and calorie burn estimation compared to single-sensor approaches. The proposed system offers a compact, energy-efficient, and cost-effective solution for continuous health monitoring and fitness tracking.

Keywords:- Calorie, Health monitoring, Max30100, nrf52840

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, to have a productive and happy life, maintaining good health is one of the important aspect. Modern lifestyle has led to various diet patterns which creates imbalance and hence individuals face health challenges such as obesity (i.e excessive weight gain), underweight and related metabolic disorders.

The physical parameters like blood oxygen, heartrate, Calorie intake, calorie burn can be monitored continuously to make a healthy lifestyle. Wearable health technology provides effective solution by offering real time monitoring and helps user to live a healthy life. Physical health is directly related to mental health well-being. Awareness. of one's daily calorie intake and expenditure helps to prevent the disorders and leads to healthy life.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

The increasing prevalence of lifestyle-related diseases such as obesity, cardiovascular disorders, and diabetes has accelerated demand for wearable health monitoring systems. Accurate calorie estimation requires both: Motion-based activity tracking Physiological parameter monitoring Traditional systems rely either on accelerometer-based step counting or heart rate-based estimation, but combining IMU and PPG signals significantly improves accuracy.

This work proposes a multi-sensor fusion approach implemented on a low-power embedded platform. The paper [1] focused on a wearable system combining PPG (on finger) + accelerometer (on ankle), transmit via Bluetooth to smartphone, and compute energy expenditure (calorie consumption) using heart rate motion. The paper [2] demonstrates that a multi-sensor wearable network (accelerometer + other physiological sensors) estimates energy expenditure (EE) more accurately than a single accelerometer (Autographs).

They use regression and neural network models. The paper [3] evaluates different combinations of sensors (accelerometer, heart rate, etc.) and builds multiple regression models to predict EE. Their method outperforms some consumer devices. The paper [4] use only IMU data (accelerometer + gyroscope) and a hybrid CNN + LSTM deep-learning model to estimate steady-state EE under various walking conditions (different speeds, inclines).

The paper [5] explains systematically study which sensor signals (HR, skin temp, SpO, acceleration, EMG, etc.) are most predictive of metabolic coat. They use multiple linear regression and cross-validation. They find combining a small number (4-5) of modalities gives good EE prediction.

METHODOLOGY

The System Architecture includes the hardware Components: nRF52840 (ARM Cortex-M4F, BLE) 6-Axis IMU (Accelerometer + Gyroscope) MAX30100 (Heart rate & SpO₂)L ion battery BLE-based mobile interface. The Seed Studio XIAO nRF52840 development board, which is a compact, powerful microcontroller board designed for low-power Bluetooth and IoT applications.

It supports powerful wireless capabilities including Bluetooth 5.0 Low Energy (BLE), NFC, and Zigbee. IMU-Based Step Counting includes acceleration peak detection crossing methods and filtering techniques, PPG-Based Heart Rate Monitoring PPG principle includes Infrared and red light absorption for SpO₂ motion artifact challenges.

The nrf52840 collects raw data from sensors through I2C/SPI interfaces. Processes and filters signals. Calculates Preliminary calorie-burn estimate using

motion and heart rate data. Manages power optimization and BLE communication. Bluetooth Low Energy Handles wireless data exchange between the wearable device and mobile system.

The wearable device is placed on the body which includes Sensors (SpO₂, temperature, IMU) measure the body parameters. The nRF52840 microcontroller collects all sensor values. The microcontroller sends data to the mobile phone using Bluetooth Low Energy. On the mobile system first user enters food items hence calories intake is calculated. With the help of data collected from Sensors calorie burnt is calculated

and system displays physical parameters like: Steps, distance, Heart rate, SpO₂, Blood pressure. User gets the comparison of calories intake and calories burnt.

The system consists of a wearable device integrated with sensors and BLE connectivity. A mobile system that provides complete caloric analysis and health tracking. A system capable of helping users maintain or correct weight through awareness of daily caloric balance. Contribution toward affordable, data-driven preventive healthcare. Encourages user to take healthy life decisions.

CONTENT

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig.1:-Block diagram

RESEARCH AND REVIEWS

By providing real-time feedback on calorie intake and expenditure, the system promotes healthier lifestyle choices, potentially reducing the risk of chronic diseases and provides accessibility the mobile app format makes it easy for users

to track their health anytime, anywhere, without the need for expensive medical devices or appointments. Awareness and Motivation: Displaying real-time statistics can help users stay motivated by visualizing their progress toward fitness goals, encouraging consistent effort.

Provides Step counting accuracy comparison (manual vs device) also accuracy vs medical oximeter power consumption measurement BLE transmission latency Calorie estimation comparison vs reference smartwatch. Step detection accuracy: ~95-97%, accuracy: ± 2 BPMB life: 3-5 days continuous monitoring Step Detection include Algorithm Raw accelerometer data acquisition (X, Y, Z axes).

Vector magnitude calculation: High-pass filtering to remove gravity Dynamic threshold peak detection Gyroscope validation to reduce false positives also Heart Rate & SpO₂ Calculation Using PPG signals: AC /DC component separation detection for BPM calculation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The implementation of real time health monitoring system based on Internet of things has achieved great results in creating awareness about underweight and obesity conditions and improving well-being of individuals. The system uses advanced technologies combination of Internet of things and embedded system to monitor health.

The system provides calculation of calories intake by entering names of food items and calculates calorie burnt by measuring physical parameters like heart rate, SpO₂, blood pressure and step count. The integration of these features fast and accurate tracking of calories estimation and allows user to understand weight balance This system helps user to avoid health disorders and promotes a healthy lifestyle.

DISCUSSION

The Sensor fusion significantly improves calorie estimation accuracy, also calculated blood pressure. Gyroscope filtering reduces false step detection. Motion artifacts affect PPG accuracy

during intense movement. Low-power optimization of nRF52840 extends battery life. It has some Challenges like Wrist vs foot placement variations, Skin tone effect on PPG and also Real-time processing constraints.

Limitations include IMU based step counting sometimes provide false step during hand motion also inaccuracy during slow walking. Many systems rely on either Heart rate or steps alone. This system combines steps, heart rate and provide calculation of calories intake and calories burnt. Limited integration of 6-axis IMU + PPG embedded systems.

The measurement of heart rate, SpO₂, blood pressure and physical activity provides calorie estimation. Mobile system displays calorie intake, calories burnt, and net calorie balance. It creates awareness of underweight or overweight conditions. Demonstrates a low-cost, portable health monitoring system.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented a wearable multi-sensor health monitoring system using the nRF52840 platform integrating IMU-based step detection and PPG-based heart rate monitoring. By combining motion and physiological parameters, the system improves calorie burn estimation accuracy compared to traditional single-sensor approaches.

The device is compact, energy efficient, and suitable for real-time continuous monitoring. Future enhancements using machine learning and cloud integration can further improve personalization and predictive healthcare capabilities.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future, the system can be modified using Machine Learning-based calorie prediction to provide more accuracy. AI-based food recognition using camera

integration based health analytics, this system uses image processing face recognition helps to provide more efficient output. Arrhythmia detection. The system can be advanced using full integration with cloud backend, advanced physiological sensors (e.g., continuous glucose monitoring), or highly sophisticated calorie-burn algorithms that require full metabolic carts.

The project will target user awareness rather than clinical diagnosis. It will focus on everyday health monitoring for both underweight and overweight users. The mobile system will run on Android (and optionally iOS), but full cross-platform deployment is optional.

Power budget optimization, miniaturization of the band, and long-term deployment (e.g., many days continuous monitoring) are desirable but may be limited by prototype time and cost constraints. Blood pressure estimation using PTT (Pulse Transit Time). Integration with IoT healthcare platforms. Integration with Google Fit / Apple Health. Cloud storage for long-term health data. Waterproof and rugged hardware design.

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